

FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO ADOPTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA AS A BUSINESS PLATFORM AMONG YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS IN WESTERN PROVINCE SRI LANKA

Savindi Fonseka¹, Mahesh Fernando², Thamali Chandrasiri³, Chandika Witharana⁴
*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura*

¹savindi.rasanga@gmail.com, ²mahesh@sjp.ac.lk, ³thamali.chandrasiri@sjp.ac.lk,
⁴chandika@sjp.ac.lk

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the process of planning, launching and operating a new business, often a small business initially. Young Entrepreneurs are people between the ages of 15 and 29 who have innovative power and entrepreneurial potential to startup their businesses (Madhushyanthi and Wijerathna, 2020). According to the survey report of Scaling Frontier Innovation (2019), not only access to capital but also entry into the market remains a barrier to entrepreneurship in Sri Lanka.

Social media has become the foremost medium for young entrepreneurs to run their businesses, including selling products and services and staying in touch with customers (Shokery et al., 2016). Spreading information more rapidly and easily help in bringing in more online customers at a very low cost, thereby expanding the market access and providing interactive features. That will enable consumers to share their experiences, feedback and opinions about products or services with their friends are some of the benefits which can obtain by using social media as a business medium (Nawaz and Mubarak, 2020).

Few previous studies have been conducted to identify the factors impacting the adoption of social media as a business platform by entrepreneurs, and most of them have been conducted particularly on student entrepreneurship in higher education institutes (Nawaz and Mubarak, 2020; Nawi et al., 2017, 2019; Rahman and Hidayat, 2019). Most of such studies have identified that the factors such as performance expectancy(PE), effort

expectancy(EE), facilitating condition(FC) , social influence(SI), perceived enjoyment(PEn), perceived risk(PR) and perceived trust(PT) affect the adoption of social media as a business platform by using the popular technology adoption theories such as Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). However, factors contributing to the adoption of social media as a business medium among young entrepreneurs in the western province of Sri Lanka have not been investigated to date and thus the motivation for research.

The adoption of social media as a business platform by young entrepreneurs has been reported to change with various factors. A study by Nawaz and Mubarak, 2020 to identify factors which impact the intention to adopt social media as a medium for business among student entrepreneurs in Sri Lanka revealed that PE, EE, FC, SI, PEn, PR has a positive and significant impact on the adoption of social media as a business platform among student entrepreneurs . Since this study has been conducted limiting only to student entrepreneurs, the authors further suggest researching factors impacting the adoption of social media as a medium for business among different groups in future (Nawaz and Mubarak, 2020).

A survey conducted by SLASSCOM with the University of Moratuwa has revealed that the highest percentage of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs are young entrepreneurs (SLASSCOM, 2016). However, hardly any research study has been conducted to explore the factors impacting the adoption of social media as a business platform among young entrepreneurs in Sri Lanka. Therefore, this research will be conducted to fulfil the research gap identified above.

The study was conducted with the research objectives of identifying factors influencing the adoption of social media as a business medium among young entrepreneurs in the Western province of Sri Lanka and identifying the relationship between each identified factor and adoption.

Methodology

A conceptual model based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), widely used in previous research, was developed as below (Nawaz and Mubarak, 2020; Nawi et al., 2017, 2019; Rahman and Hidayat, 2019).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

This study followed a deductive approach in quantitative research methodology and used a cross-sectional study to collect data only once from a sample using an online questionnaire. The online questionnaire (google form) has been disseminated to selected young entrepreneurs in Western province mainly through young entrepreneurs' Facebook groups, LinkedIn, WhatsApp messages and other social media platforms. The sample size calculated using multiple regression of Daniel Soper's sample size calculator was 103. Analysis was performed using multiple regression techniques with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Results and Discussion

From descriptive data analysis, the majority of respondents (73.4%) belonged to the age category 20 - 24 and were males 77.1% (n=84). The

majority of them had less than one year of experience (43%) with social media as a business medium. The reliability and validity of constructs were evaluated before model testing. The Cronbach's alpha above the 0.7 threshold indicated that the variables were proven as consistent and reliable (Hair et al., 2014). Also, the study was proven to have face validity, content validity and construct validity. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value for the study was 0.831, which denotes that the sample is adequate to test the model.

Additionally, Bartlett's test of sphericity value was reported as less than 0.05, confirming the suitability for factor analysis. According to Hair et al., (2014), the Extraction (factor loading) should be greater than 0.5 in each indicator to satisfy the factor loading. The data analysis confirmed the factor loading adequacy for all variables in this study. The Pearson correlation coefficient is positive in all the cases. All variables except Perceived Risk (PR) had a significant positive correlation with behavioral intention.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Table (Correlation Matrix with Dependent Variable)

Variables	Behavioral Intention (BI)
Performance Expectancy (PE)	0.704**
Effort Expectancy (EE)	0.604**
Social Influence (SI)	0.583**
Facilitating Condition (FC)	0.651**
Perceived Enjoyment (PE _n)	0.694**
Perceived Risk (PR)	0.246**
Perceived Trust (PT)	0.510**
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 confidence level (2-tailed)	

The four assumptions tests of Multiple Linear Regression (linearity test, homoscedasticity, multicollinearity, and normality test) were conducted to

ensure the appropriateness of data to assumptions of regression analysis, which aren't violated in the study.

In the Multiple regression analysis, the determinant of coefficient (R^2) of the study is 0.651, which demonstrates that 65% of the variability in the behavioral intention to adopt social media as a business platform is explained by the model's independent variables. The p-value of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is lower than 0.05 (even lower than 0.01), statistically confirming that the model of this study can explain the dependent variable. The hypotheses test result are exhibited in Table 2.

Table 2: Hypotheses Testing Results

Hypotheses	Beta Coefficient	T Value	Hypotheses Result (95% Confidence)
H1	0.312	3.654***	Accepted
H2	0.073	0.863	Rejected
H3	0.145	1.931	Rejected
H4	0.190	2.175**	Accepted
H5	0.224	2.329**	Accepted
H6	0.016	0.250	Rejected
H7	0.037	0.483	Rejected
Note: *** $p < 0.01$ ** $p < 0.05$			

Based on the hypotheses testing results, the multiple regression equation can be stated as:

$$\text{Behavioral Intention (BI)} = 0.243 + 0.318 (\text{PE}) + 0.199 (\text{FC}) + 0.216 (\text{PEn})$$

Conclusion

From the hypotheses testing results, only three hypotheses were supported. Performance expectancy strongly influenced young entrepreneurs' behavioural intention to adopt social media as a business platform. Perceived enjoyment was the second most important factor, which could be interpreted as young entrepreneurs realising the fun and enjoyment related to adopting social media as a business medium. Also, facilitating conditions had a significant and positive impact, implying that young entrepreneurs find it vital to have the necessary support and help while using social media as a business platform. Future studies could be conducted using the same conceptual model with a wider sample and additional variables.

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